

Potential of Some Major Indian Tropical Fruits (Banana, Guava, Papaya) to Produce Enzyme-Clarified Juice and its Impact on Indian Processed Fruit Industry

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Abstract

India is second largest producer of fruits in the world. The main tropical fruits produced in India include mango, banana, guava, papaya, pineapple, and litchi (or lychee) and to a lesser extent sapota, phalsa, jackfruit, annona and ber. Still the current processing and export volumes of these fruits are very small. Juice and juice products represent a very important segment of today's processed fruit industry. Today consumers have grown accustomed to the manifold possibilities of buying apple, orange, mango, pomegranate and other juices, independently of the geographic location or season. Juice clarification is very important process for modern juice processing industry because it enhances the acceptability of the product. For the preparation of ready to serve drinks, jelly, cordials, nutritional carbonated beverages, concentrates, nectars, etc., clarified juices are in high demand. The use of enzymes has been an essential part of the entire technology of juice production. Enzymatic treatment results in degradation of pectin and viscosity reduction which facilitates separation through filtration or centrifugation giving the juice higher clarity. Currently pectinases, cellulases and hemicellulases, collectively called macerating enzymes are used for extraction and clarification of fruit juices.

Introduction

Juice clarification is very important process for juice processing industry because it enhances the acceptability of the product (Phing&Kalam, 2023, Sharma et al. 2015). Juices with unacceptable cloud and muddy turbidity are undesirable for marketing. (Kaushal et al., 2021, Shah & Nath 2007). For the preparation of ready to serve drinks, jelly, cordials, nutritional carbonated beverages, concentrates, nectars, etc., clarified juices are in high demand (Brito et al. 2008). A variety of products based on clarified juice such as sparkling clear beverages (soft drinks, clear juice cocktails, alcoholic beverages, cold teas with clear juice), translucent jelly products, candies, clear juice blends, fruit honey or fruit sugar, 100% canned fruit (with clear juice as syrup) etc. are making place in the market. This shows that there exist several market opportunities, not only for the traditional clear juice from apple, but also for clarified juices produced from fruits with high pulp content (Sakhale et al., 2016, Vaillant et al. 2001).

Today, India is second largest producer of fruits and vegetables. It accounts for about 10.4 per cent of all fruits and nearly 40 per cent of tropical fruits produced globally. The main tropical fruits produced in India include banana, guava, mango, papaya, pineapple, and litchi. Still the current processing and export volumes are very small. On a comparative basis globally, only 2 per cent of the fruit production in India is processed. Most of the fruits India is producing are consumed domestically. Export volumes remains less than 1 percent of total domestic output, as well as less than 1 percent of world exports. It is estimated that about 4.6 to 15.9 per cent of fruit and vegetable production is wasted due to a lack of post-harvest infrastructure (MOFPI, 2023).

The number of health conscious consumers is increasing in India, especially in urban areas. They are not consuming beverages only for their thirst quenching properties and convenience care but are more focused on nutrition and functionality in them and so the juice market in India is growing. The overall soft drink market in India saw aggregate sales of over 20,000 million litres (worth Rs. 65,330 crore) in 2014. The main segments that constitute the soft drink market in India are juices and bottled water, carbonates, which together accounted for 99 per cent of the total volumes in 2014. Ready-to-drink tea, sports and energy drinks and concentrates account for the remainder. The fruit-based juice market is one of the fastest-growing categories in the beverage segment. It is growing at a CAGR (compound annual growth rate) of 25-30 per cent in the past decade. The juice market in India is estimated to be around Rs. 10,781.62 crore (16 per cent of the total soft drink market in India). The juice business in India is highly dominated by unorganised players having a market share of over 75 per cent. The organised retail that has only 25 per cent of the business comprises juice bars, juice cafes and packaged juice players. The fruit juice market in India is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 22 per cent over the next five years, and is expected to grow more than double in the next few years (Food & Beverage News, 2016).

Juice Clarification by Enzymatic Treatment

Clarification is the process of breaking the semistable emulsion of colloidal plant carbohydrates that support the insoluble cloud material in a freshly extracted juice. Enzymatic treatment of juices results in degradation of pectin and viscosity reduction which facilitates separation through filtration or centrifugation giving the juice higher clarity. Currently pectinases, cellulases and hemicellulases, collectively called macerating enzymes are used for extraction and clarification of fruit juices (Hossain & Ahmed, 2023). Pectinases hydrolyses α -1,4-glycosidic linkages of pectin molecules and produce polygalacturonic acid monomers (Grassin and Fauquembergue, 1996). Cellulases cleaves β -1,4-D-glucan linkages of cellulose to yield oligosaccharides, cellobiose and glucose (Beguin and Daubert, 1994, Henrissat, 1994) while hemicellulases are a diverse group of enzymes that hydrolyse hemicelluloses, one of the most abundant group of polysaccharide found in nature (Sharma et al., 2014). The use of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes in combination for juice clarification enhances the yield and clarity because of simultaneous degradation of polysaccharides (Pal and Khanum, 2011). The effect of hydrolytic enzymes on juice extraction and clarification have been reported in banana (Sharma et al., 2016, Tapre & Jain, 2014, Sagu et al., 2014, Cheersilp & Umsakul, 2008, Tadakittisarn et al., 2007 and Lee et al., 2006, Yunchalad et al., 1995, Kotecha et al., 1994, Pheantaveerat and Anprung 1993 and Koffi et al., 1991), guava (Akesowan & Choonhahirun, 2013, Sevda et al. 2012, Thi et al., 2012, Kaur et al., 2011), litchi (Vijayanand et al. 2010, Shah and Nath, 2007), mango (Anuradha et al., 2016, Ndiaye et al., 2011), kiwifruit (Vaidya et al., 2009, Dawes et al., 1994), papaya (Tu et al. 2013, Dzogbefia & Djokoto, 2006), apple (Ozyilmaz & Gunay, 2023, Pilnik et al., 1975; Voragen et al., 1980), pineapple (Dzogbefia et al., 2001, Sreenath et al., 1994), asparagus (Chen et al., 2012), peach (Santin et al., 2008), pear (Joshi et al., 2011), carrot (Uzuner and Cekmecelioglu, 2015, Alam et al. 2014) and plums (Chang et al., 1995).

Banana

Banana is a tropical fruit of high nutritional quality with its widely appreciated flavour and aroma. It is one of the abundant and cheap fruits in India. The country ranks first in production of Bananas (26.45%) (APEDA, 2023). However, only 0.05% of production of banana is exported and the rest is consumed within the country as table fruit. Although, in international trade banana is the most popular one and ranks second after citrus fruits in terms of value, India, largest banana producing country is hardly involved in it. The causes behind low volume export of banana include non-ideal post-harvest practices, transport practices, improper storage facilities, and outdated banana handling practices. Because of mishandling of produce about 25-40% is being wasted and only 2% is processed into value added products. Since bananas can be pulped, juiced or concentrated, canned, sliced and dried, there are huge opportunity of processing of banana for preparation of derivative products. Beverages such as banana wine, banana brandy and vinegar can be made economically. (NHB, 2022).

Fruit juices are generally extracted by crushing and grinding. Juices obtained by these operations are viscous, turbid and cloudy. This happens due to the presence of pulp particles and colloidal suspensions. Yield of this kind of juices is low and it is very difficult to concentrate and pasteurize them. In case of banana also crushing and grinding do not yield juice from banana as bananas are too pulpy and pectinaceous (Adao and Gloria, 2005). A sticky and lumpy mass is obtained after these operations with banana. The most severe problem associated with banana pulp processing is high viscosity. The viscosity and turbidity of banana juice are caused mainly by the polysaccharides in the juice such as pectin and starch(Lee et al. 2006).

Effect of Enzymatic Treatment on Banana Juice

Different researchers have used different commercial enzymes in banana pulp processing.

Tapre & Jain (2014) optimized the enzymatic clarification process of banana pulp of maturity stage 6 using RSM (response surface methodology). The pulp was treated with pectinase enzyme at concentrations (0.05-0.15%), temperature (30-50 °C) and incubation time (60-180 min) of treatment. The effect of these enzymatic conditions on % yield, viscosity and clarity of banana juice were studied. The optimum conditions for clarification of banana pulp found were: 0.12% enzyme concentration, 38.84 °C incubation temperature and 136.52 min of incubation time that resulted yield, viscosity and clarity of juice under above conditions, 64.76%, 450.20 cps and 84.56%, respectively.

Sagu, Karmakar, et al. (2014) extracted banana juice by pectinase treatment at room temperature. The resultant juice was clarified by two methods- centrifugation and microfiltration. A comparative study was performed between these two methods. To optimize the parameters of centrifugation (speed and time) and microfiltration (transmembrane pressure and cross flow rate) RSM was used. The juice was analysed in terms of viscosity, clarity, alcohol insoluble solids (AIS), polyphenol, and protein content. Centrifuged juice was found to contain high concentration of total polyphenol and protein. Juice obtained from microfiltration had lower AIS, viscosity and higher clarity. The energy consumption of the centrifuge is also much higher than that of microfiltration.

Sagu, Nso, et al. (2014) developed a process with optimum conditions for banana juice. The banana pulp was hydrolyzed by commercial pectinase followed by cloth filtration. RSM was utilised to optimize the process parameters. The independent variables were incubation temperature (30-60 °C), reaction time (20-120 min) and pectinase concentration (0.01-0.05% v/w) and the responses were viscosity, clarity, alcohol insoluble solids, total polyphenol and protein concentration. The results showed reduction of AIS (alcohol insoluble solids) and viscosity with reaction time and enzyme concentration. Reduction of polyphenol and protein concentration with temperature were also observed.

Cheirsilp and Umsakul (2008) used the enzymes pectinase and α -amylase to hydrolyse pectin and starch (prior to use of the juice to produce a wine product) to treat banana must. The synergistic activities of the enzymes enhanced hydrolysis of the complex carbohydrates. A 55% decrease in viscosity and a 2.7-fold increase in the amount of extracted juice were observed after incubating with 0.05% (w/w) of pectinase at 40 °C for 2 h, followed by treating with 0.05% (w/w) of α -amylase at 50 °C for 3 h. A 15% and 39% increase in total soluble sugars and reducing sugars in extracted juice were achieved, respectively. Enzyme-treated banana must was given dilution with four volumes of water and then fermentation was carried out by yeast to produce banana wine. The pre-treatment of banana with enzymes before fermentation resulted in a higher level of reducing sugars than that of nonenzyme-treated banana wine (the control) during fermentation. The clarity of the enzyme-treated banana wine was also found fourfold higher than that of the control at 25 days of fermentation. No significant differences were found in the concentrations of total soluble solids (TSS), total

soluble sugars, and alcohol in the enzyme-treated banana wine and the control.

Tadakittisarn et al. (2007) optimized the pectinase enzyme liquefaction of banana „GrosMicheal“ pulp by RSM. The effect of pectinase enzyme concentrations (0-0.2%) and incubation times (60-300 min) on juice yield (%), TSS (total soluble solids), RSS (recovery soluble solids), clarity (% T₆₇₀) and browning index (A₄₂₀) of juice were studied. The optimum condition found for enzymatic extraction was 0.15% of pectinase enzyme incubated for 120 min at 50°C. The yield was $\geq 62\%$, $RSS \geq 14$, $\%T_{670} \geq 96\%$ and $A_{420} \leq 0.1$.

Lee et al, (2006) studied on optimization of conditions for the enzymatic clarification of banana juice using RSM. Banana juice was treated with pectinase at various enzyme concentrations (0.01– 0.1%), temperatures (30–50 °C) and treatment time (30–120 min). The effect of these treatments on juice properties filterability, clarity, viscosity and turbidity of the juice were studied. The optimum conditions for clarifying the banana juice found were: 0.084% enzyme concentration, incubation temperature of 43.2 °C and incubation time of 80 min.

Shahadan and Abdullah (1995) determined the optimum conditions for extraction of banana juice. RSM was used for optimization. The effects of temperature (20-50 °C), pH (2.7-4.3) and enzyme concentration (0.13-0.47%) on the yield of banana juice were studied after a 4h time of reaction. The optimal conditions for the enzymatic extraction of banana juice found were 0.42% enzyme at 35 °C with a pH of 3.4.

Yunchand et al, (1995) prepared the clarified banana juice by using commercial enzyme pectinase and amyloglucosidase to increase juice yield. The optimum concentration found was 0.03% Pectinex Ultra SP-L or Rohapex TF with 0.02% amyloglucosidase. Juice yield reached about 80%, when the banana puree was preheated to 90 °C in steam blancher, followed by enzyme treatment at 45 °C and maintained for 2 hrs.

Kotecha et al, (1994) carried out preliminary studies to carry out banana juice extraction by using different levels of pectinase enzymes and different levels of incubation periods at 28±2 °C. Based on these studies a 0.2% pectinase addition and a 4h incubation time were selected for obtaining the juice from pulp. Centrifugation was used to separate the juice and the clear juice was used for preparation of juice.

Pheantaveerat and Anprung (1993) studied the application of commercially available pectinases, cellulases and amylases for hydrolysis of ripe banana pulp. He observed that the synergistic activities of enzymes in increasing degree of pulp hydrolysis expressed as percent decreased viscosity of juice obtained after the pulp was incubated with 0.06% by weight of cellulases and with 0.05% by weight of pectinases at 45 °C for 2 h. Under such condition, the clear juice yield of 73% (base on pulp weight used) was obtained. Furthermore, amylases were not effective to the above activity.

Koffi et al, (1991) conducted experiments to determine the effects of commercial enzyme preparations on filterability and reduction in viscosity of banana juice. The effectiveness of various anti-browning treatments on clarified juice was also determined. Two different combinations of pectinase, cellulase and hemicellulase were more effective in reducing viscosity and improving filterability of both green and ripe banana purees than a pectinase, galactomannanase or cellulase after periods of incubation of 3, 6 and 9 h. An alpha-amylase was not effective in reducing viscosity as compared to the control, even of green banana puree high in starch.

Viquez et al, (1981) studied the effect of pectinolytic enzyme treatments on banana pulp to on yield, viscosity and clarity of the juice. Juice yields of between 55 and 60% are obtained from pulp that was incubated at 45°C for 1 hr with 0.01% (w/w) of enzyme by subsequent centrifugation. This corresponds to a yield of total and reducing sugars present in the pulp of over 75%. Untreated control pulps yield less than 5% of juice under these conditions. Hydraulic pressing of the pulps at 16 kg/cm² gives similar yields to those obtained by centrifugation.

Guava

Guava is one of the important commercial tropical fruits in India. It is known as the poor man's apple of the tropics (Singh et al. 2014). It is available throughout the year except during the summer season. It gives an assured crop with little care. Its requirements for fertilizer, irrigation and plant protection are not much and so its cost of production is also low. Further it is of very high nutritive value and so it is often considered as super fruit. It is rich in vitamins A and C (in the pericarp), omega-3 and -6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (in the seeds) and have high levels of dietary fibre. A single guava fruit weighing 160-170 g contains over four times more of vitamin 'C' compared to a single orange (220-230 mg per 100g) and also has adequate levels of dietary minerals, potassium, and magnesium. (Khan et al. 2013). Along with its nutritional properties, this fruit is very appetizing due to its sensory (flavor and color) properties (Rahel et al. 2015). Guava is also grown as a backyard fruit. India ranks first in production of guavas (APEDA, 2023). In India, the best quality guavas are produced in Uttar Pradesh, particularly in Allahabad region. Guava fruits are consumed either fresh or processed. However, only 0.05% of the produce is being exported to foreign countries. (NHB, 2022).

The ripened guava is highly perishable when kept at ambient temperature. Therefore, it is processed in various commercial guava products that include paste, puree, juice, canned slices. The guava juice has become economically important in the market among these products. The consumption of tropical fruit juice like guava juice has been increasing currently as it is natural, high in nutritional value and may be used as an alternative to other beverages such as soft drinks, coffee and tea (Akesowan & Choonhahirun 2013). A grit-free, haze-free and clear guava juice is preferred by a significant portion of the population. Clarified guava juice may be more acceptable to the general population, and may be used in the manufacturing of products that are based on clear juice e.g. clear guava nectar, clear jelly, clear guava powder or a mixed juice blend. (Chopda & Barrett 2001). The flavour and aroma of guava are highly appreciated and is able to compete in the market, either as guava juice or as mixtures with other fruit juices. However, the fresh guava juice is gray in colour, turbid, very viscous and tends to settle during storage. (Younis et al. 2014) Fruit juices are generally extracted by crushing and grinding. Juices obtained by these operations are viscous, turbid and cloudy. This happens due to the presence of pulp particles and colloidal suspensions. Yield of this kind of juices is low and it is very difficult to concentrate and pasteurize them. The guava juice is conventionally processed by mechanical pressing of guava mash. Raw guava juice is gray in colour, very viscous and turbid. Pectin substances, that are composed of partially methyl-esterified galacturonic acid residues linked by α -1,4-glycosidic bonds, are responsible for the turbidity and viscosity of guava juice. (Sevda et al. 2012).

Effect of Enzymatic Treatment on Guava Juice

Most of the researchers have used pectinase enzyme in Guava pulp processing.

Akesowan & Choonhahirun (2013) used Response surface methodology (RSM) to study the effects of pectinase (Pectinex Ultra SP-L), enzyme concentration (500-900 ppm), and incubation time (30-90 min) on viscosity of guava puree and pH, TA (titratable acidity), clarity, yield, TSS and ascorbic acid content of guava juice. The enzyme treatment promoted juice clarification, reduced guava puree viscosity, and increased values for TA, yield, TSS and ascorbic acid content of guava juice than that without enzyme. They recommended optimal enzyme treatment (869.36 ppm pectinase in guava mash and incubation time 71.27 min) before filtration process. Under this condition, predicted puree viscosity, yield, TSS and ascorbic acid content were 160.07 cps, 85.10%, 5.60 °Brix and 54.27 mg/100 ml, respectively. They concluded that, the development of guava juice quality can be achieved by application of pectinase enzyme. The study found that increasing of enzyme concentration and incubation time is related to decrease in guava puree viscosity and increase in yield, TSS and ascorbic acid content of guava juice.

Sevda et. al. (2012) optimized the enzymatic clarification process of guava juice using RSM. Guava

juice was given treatment with pectinase at various enzyme concentrations (0.01-0.2%), temperatures (30-50°C) and incubation time (30-150 min). The effect of enzyme treatments on % yield, clarity, turbidity, titrable acidity and viscosity of the juice were studied. The optimum conditions for clarifying guava juice obtained were: enzyme concentration of 0.11%, incubation temperature of 41.30°C and incubation time of 115.98 min with % yield (80.03%), clarity (1.34 Abs), turbidity (1.07 Abs), titrable acidity (0.525%), viscosity (2.4 cps) and desirability of 0.942.

Thi et al. (2012) used cellulase preparation in guava mash treatment for improvement in juice yield and quality. The effect of enzyme concentration and biocatalytic time on the juice yield was studied. RSM was then used to select enzyme dose and incubation time for maximizing juice yield. Optimal conditions found were concentration of cellulase preparation 0.13% (w/w) and treatment time 93 minutes. Under these conditions, the increase in extraction yield, total sugars and phenolics level in the juice were found to be 22.3%, 20.0% and 11.5%, respectively in comparison with those in the control sample. Treatment with cellulase decreased the ascorbic acid content in guava juice and the antioxidant activity of the product was increased 21.8% in comparison with that in the control sample.

Kaur et al. (2011) treated guava juice with commercial pectinase and used RSM to optimize the incubation temperature (36.6–53.4 °C), incubation time (0.95–11.05 h) and enzyme concentration (0.16–0.84 mg/100 g guava pulp) on ascorbic acid retention, viscosity clarity, and colour (L value) of guava juice. The compromised optimum condition obtained for clarifying guava juice were: incubation temperature 45.35 °C, incubation time 7.23 h and enzyme concentration 0.70 g per 100 g guava pulp with ascorbic acid 77.71 mg per 100 g, clarity 34.54%, viscosity 1.24 cps and color (L value) 23.33.

Kaur et al. (2009) studied the effect of enzyme (commercial pectinase) concentration (0.16–0.84 mg per 100 g guava pulp), incubation temperature (36.6– 53.4 °C), and incubation time (0.95–11 h) on juice yield. The recommended enzymatic treatment condition was at the enzyme concentration 0.70 mg per 100 g guava pulp, incubation time 7.27 h, and incubation temperature 43.3 °C.

Papaya

Papaya is a tropical fruit and is commonly known for its nutritive, medicinal as well as economic value. It is good source of antioxidant nutrients (e.g., carotenes, vitamin C, and flavonoids), the B vitamins (e.g., folate and pantothenic acid), minerals (e.g., potassium and magnesium), and fiber (Evans & Ballen 2015). It has long been cultivated in the home gardens of people. It is the crop that bears fruit throughout the year. India ranks first in production of papaya (39.30%) (APEDA, 2023).

Papaya is gaining popularity worldwide, but only 0.08% of domestic production is exported and the rest is consumed within the country. (NHB, 2022). In India, the post-harvest losses of papaya are estimated at 5-30 percent of total production. The mechanical injured and over ripen papaya fruits are wasted in large quantities due to absence of facilities, improper handling, distribution, marketing and lack of storage facilities. These losses can be minimized by processing of papaya fruit that also gives better return to farmer during the glut season. Under ambient tropical conditions, freshly harvested, ripe papaya fruit typically exhibit a storage potential of less than one week (Shashikalabai et al. 2016). Fruit juices are generally extracted by crushing and grinding. Juices obtained by these operations are viscous, turbid and cloudy. This happens due to the presence of pulp particles and colloidal suspensions. Yield of this kind of juices is low and it is very difficult to concentrate and pasteurize them. In case of papaya also crushing and grinding do not yield juice from papaya as papayas are too pulpy and pectinaceous. Due to its high pectin content, a sticky and lumpy mass is obtained rather than juice after these operations.

Effect of Enzymatic treatment on papaya

Not much literature is available about the papaya pulp clarification. However, some researchers have tried enzyme application in papaya pulp.

Tu et al. (2013) identified a novel endo-polygalacturonase (endo-PG I) from *Achaetomium* sp. Xz8, overexpressed in *Pichia pastoris*, and characterized. Recombinant endo-PG I is distinguished from other enzyme counterparts by its high activity towards polygalacturonic acid (49,934 U/ml) and high yield in the 15-l fermenter (2.13 g/l). It exhibits optimal activity at 45 °C and remained active over a broad temperature range of 0–80 °C. Most fungal polygalacturonases have acidic pH optima. Distinct from most fungal polygalacturonases, endo-PG I is optimally active at pH 6, similar to the pH of fresh papaya juice (5.7). Endo-PG was employed in papaya juice. It alone reduced the viscosity of papaya juice by 17.6%, and increased its transmittance by 59.1%. In combination with a commercial pectin methylesterase, it showed much higher efficiency with a synergy degree of more than 1.25. All these favourable enzymatic properties make endo-PG I attractive for potential applications in the juice industry.

Dzoghbeia & Djokoto (2006) produced pectic enzymes from a strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (ATCC 52712) and used it in different applications including fruit juice extraction. The enzyme was produced in the laboratory. The yeast was cultured in papaya juice supplemented with 1% pectin for 6 days. Known amounts of enzyme preparation (0–40 mg protein) were added to a measured weight of papaya mash for varying reaction periods (30–90 min). The amount of free-run juice obtained in each treatment was compared with a control sample. 200 g of papaya mash treated with different dosages of the pectic enzyme extract that resulted in rapid increase in flow rate of free-run juice. Mash treated with 32 mg of total protein extract with a 30-min reaction time was found optimum for a maximum rate of juice flow (25 mL/min) when initial rates were measured. No significant difference was observed ($P > 0.05$) between the red- and yellow-fleshed varieties of the papaya used. When juice flow was observed over 6 min, the treated samples gave a flow rate that was more than twice those of the untreated samples. This biotechnological approach could be adopted to enhance papaya-juice production by local fruit juice processors. Sreenath and Santhanam (1994) treated pulps of fruits papaya, watermelon, cantaloupe, jackfruit, and tamarind with a commercial pectinase and a cellulase, and found a marginal improvement in juice yield and/or juice clarity.

Clarified juices: Future Prospects

Clarified juices have a good consumer acceptability because of its sparkling and attractive appearance and so a high market value. Clarified juices can play an important role in increasing the country's export volumes which is presently negligible, although India is one of the world's largest fruit producers. Retail sales of fruit juices in foreign market is considerably high, and thus higher foreign revenue can be earned by the export of clarified fruit juices. Wastage of fruits which is about 25 to 30 percent of fruit production (very high) can be minimized by utilizing the raw produce for the production of high quality processed product. More than 80 percent of fruit exports from India are tropical fruits, including mangoes, guava, pineapples, and papayas. Clarified juices produced from tropical fruits may prove a good alternative in processed fruit sector.

Conclusion

In spite of India's first rank in production of banana, guava and papaya, the current processing and export volume of these fruits are negligible. Although these fruits are pulpy in nature, but they have good potential of producing high value clarified juices by the application of enzymes. Enzymatic treatment is most commonly used nowadays for juice extraction and clarification. Various fruit juices treated with pectinases, cellulases, hemicellulases, amylases etc. results in higher yield of juice and improves quality characteristics such as clarity, viscosity, browning index, colour etc. Different enzymes in combination claim to increase juice yield, clarity, TSS, and decrease in viscosity. Many modern processes of fruit juice production frequently use pectinases, but mixtures of cellulytic and pectolytic enzymes may enhance pulp liquefaction and higher juice yield with higher soluble solid content. Therefore, clarified juices may be developed from these fruits which may contribute in increasing India's processed fruit and export volume.

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